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**CASE OF TEACHING A PROFESSIONAL FOREIGN LANGUAGE (ENGLISH) AT
A NON-LINGUISTIC FACULTY IN THE PROFILE OF JOURNALISM**

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Abstract: *This article explores the challenges and strategies of teaching a professional foreign language (English) to journalism students at a non-linguistic faculty. With only one semester allocated for professionally oriented language training, the study highlights the need for a tailored approach to material selection, student engagement, and assessment. The article presents practical experiences, emphasizing authenticity, interactivity, and cultural relevance. Key methods included reflective essays, peer evaluations, and a student-driven final project (e.g., interviews or reports). Results demonstrated improved professional vocabulary, critical thinking, and motivation, though challenges such as uneven language proficiency and demands for clearly formulated criteria were noted. The study emphasizes the importance of flexibility, well-developed rubrics, and dialogue between a teacher and students to optimize learning outcomes in constrained timeframes.*

Keywords: *professional foreign language teaching, non-linguistic faculties, journalism education, authentic materials, student-centered learning, reflective essays, peer assessment, interactivity in language learning, curriculum design*

Foreign language training in Russian universities usually takes place over several semesters, with the exact number of semesters depending on the educational program and level of preparation. On average, a foreign language is studied for 6 to 8 semesters in a bachelor's degree, sometimes continuing in a master's degree. The number of semesters and hours may vary depending on the profile of preparation and the form of study. At Dostoevsky Omsk State University, in the bachelor's degree of non-linguistic specialties, foreign language study takes 3 semesters: basic foreign language is studied during the 1st and 2nd semesters of the 1st year, and a professional foreign language - in the 3rd semester (2nd year). Due to the limited time of the program, teachers face a hugely complex task: to organize the learning process so that in addition to developing linguistic skills (after all, those entering the university have different levels of knowledge), students study topics focused on their future professions, enrich the specific vocabulary associated with them, and comprehend the specifics of their future profession through foreign-language materials.

The difficulties in organizing the learning process at this crucial moment, when the transition from basic learning of a foreign language to professional learning takes place, require studying and analyzing practical experience. In this article, I want to share my experience of teaching a professional foreign language, namely English, at a non-linguistic faculty in the profile of journalism, hoping to invite colleagues to a discussion and that what is written below will bring new ideas and approaches to teaching.

PRINCIPLES OF SELECTION OF STUDY MATERIAL:

Selection of teaching materials is the key to the success of foreign language teaching and requires a comprehensive approach taking into account the specifics of the professional field, the level of students' language, and modern pedagogical technologies. The use of high-quality, relevant resources, their adaptation to specific needs can ensure effective teaching and preparation of students for real-life professional situations. The importance of this stage is also associated with several controversial issues that are proposed to be considered through the prism of the main criteria for selecting materials for professionally oriented foreign language teaching:

- **Compliance with the goals and objectives of the course.** It is indisputable that the materials should reflect the professional needs of students and the specifics of their future activities so that their learning experience is relevant and useful for their professional life. Thus, it is important to carefully

analyze the needs of students and the goals of the course before choosing materials - this is important for maintaining a high level of motivation of students and reflects the motivational and cognitive value of the material.

- **Authenticity and cultural relevance.** It is desirable to use authentic materials, not just created in a foreign language, but also reflecting real professional communication. At the same time, it is worth recognizing that the choice in favor of educational materials adapted or created taking into account Russian realities can be applied much more effectively in groups of intermediate language level and below: it is important to give tasks that are an intellectual challenge for students, but they should not lead to disappointment and a decrease in motivation for learning.

It is also possible to follow the parallel study of basic language topics with the introduction of professionally oriented materials and tasks, using a combination of a textbook and additional authentic materials. In any case, the teacher must be flexible and understand the pedagogical validity of the teaching material used, which should be adaptable to different levels of preparation and learning styles and also include auxiliary tools aimed at mastering aspects that are difficult for students (e.g. exercises, multimedia resources).

- In the modern world, where the speed of change is ever higher, emerging new knowledge and technologies are transforming the professional landscape, one should not neglect the factor of **novelty of educational materials** specifically for a professional foreign language, because if they lag behind modern realities, students will lack interest in the subject.

PRACTICAL EXPERIENCE in selecting a textbook and developing a strategy for working with it:

The practical experience described concerns teaching professional English to a group of students majoring in Journalism and Media Communication with English levels ranging from A2 to B2. The chosen textbook to teach professional English to this group was **Writing & Reporting for the Media**, 3rd edition, by John R. Bender (2019). This is a fundamental textbook on journalism in English that introduces students to the specifics of professional activity (professional, ethical principles, etc.) and is focused on developing practical skills through analysis of topics and examples: it takes students through the stages from formulating ideas for stories, collecting information, interviewing sources to creating different types of news stories. The text uses clear, accessible language, provides numerous examples, and a variety of realistic practical exercises at the end of each chapter give students the opportunity to apply and improve studied skills.

Having chosen good teaching materials in English, it was not possible to avoid problems. Due to the peculiarities of the educational program at Omsk State University (3 semester of the bachelor's degree is allocated for a professionally oriented foreign language), difficulties emerged because, at that point, students lacked adequate professional knowledge and hands-on experience, which led to challenges in grasping the material. To resolve controversial situations (when students did not have enough practical skills or knowledge), students always asked for expert opinion from the teachers of the department who taught special disciplines.

It is also necessary to note the difference in the presentation and vision of professional topics: in the specific case of journalism, there were noticeable differences in the recommended methods of preparation for writing articles and conducting interviews, the specifics of the structural division of articles, etc.; but it was precisely this that gave students the opportunity to understand the cultural characteristics of the professional sphere in foreign countries, enriching their experience in practical and analytical work in the professional sphere.

From student reviews:

Was the training material useful, and how?

Answer: The training material was useful due to the large amount of information about working as a journalist, about the “pitfalls” of working in this field. Many thanks to the various reminders and articles from professional journalists. I really hope to use all of this in my future work.

Elizaveta S.

I learned a lot of things from the world of media, the existence of which I did not even know about. I think the information I received will definitely pay off in the future.

Ulyana P.

Since the subject was to teach the basics of journalism in English using authentic materials in a mixed-level group, it was necessary to develop a WORK SCHEME that would take into account the linguistic background of all students. Given that the book is divided into chapters, the strategy was that students would study certain material in advance, coming to class prepared. This strategy was presented at the first class of the semester, and students were invited to suggest their changes and improvements, including during the course of the semester.

The lesson included a review of the material: first, lexical - two students were selected for each chapter, who were responsible for compiling a professionally oriented English–Russian dictionary, which was posted for general use in a study group (specially created in VK), the most complex jargon terms were discussed for translation (e.g., hard news, soft news, proximity) or, if they did not have analogues, transliterations with explanations (e.g., lead, nut graph). The preliminary training provided an opportunity for everyone not only to familiarize themselves with the content, but also to learn a vocabulary that was useful both for the discussion of the topics and for doing classroom assignments. Then the substantive elements were discussed: students formulated their opinions on the key ideas of the section, answered questions on the content, and completed additional tasks, both with preliminary preparation and spontaneously.

When discussing the chapter on professional ethics of journalists, students prepared reports on how this area is regulated in Russia, compared it with the ethical code of the Society of Professional Journalists given in the textbook, what’s more, students gave their opinion on how they see professional ethical standards for journalists in the future. Another example of an additional practical task on the analyzed material is a competition for writing the best leads, in which students completed tasks on evaluating and analyzing the leads presented in the textbook, shortening the proposed leads, and writing their own leads. At each stage, there was a parallel discussion of the difficulties, and the students themselves were engaged in evaluating the results of the last two competitions through voting with likes in a discussion in a study group on VK.

Attachment 1. Example of a competition for the best leads.

The textbook material includes practical assignments at the end of most chapters, which allowed the discussed theoretical aspects to be applied in practice. However, the most important final stage of each analyzed chapter was writing a reflective essay (as homework), in which students analyzed the studied material, highlighted difficult moments for them, formulated the remaining unresolved questions (if any), listed what they remembered most, and significant takeaways. Before writing the first essay, its structure and content were discussed in the group. All essays were also posted in the study group on VK for subsequent work with them.

Attachment 2. Example of analysis of the Reflective essay topic.

- ✓ Brainstorm your thoughts, feelings, and reactions to the topic.
- ✓ Create an outline to organize your reflections into a cohesive structure.
- ✓ Write an engaging introduction that sets the stage and introduces your main idea or thesis.
- ✓ Develop the body paragraphs, delving into specific experiences, insights, and lessons learned.
- ✓ Use personal examples and details to support your reflections.
- ✓ Conclude by summarizing your key points and reflecting on the broader significance of your experiences.

Subsequently, all essays were assessed by the students themselves (as homework) using blind drawing (students drew cards with names of their classmates). This format was also new at first and raised questions among the students, but as practice was accumulated, most of the difficulties were resolved. Students' assessment of each other's work became an important element of learning, involving them emotionally in the learning process, improving their analytical, linguistic and interpersonal skills, promoting the development of critical thinking, and increasing motivation for self-improvement and improving academic performance, both individual and group.

From student reviews:

Was the format of knowledge testing at the end of each chapter through a reflective essay effective? Answer: A reflective essay is an interesting format, because we could fully analyze the chapter and allow ourselves to share thoughts, conduct the so-called "self-reflection".

Was the experience of assessing the work of classmates useful; in what way? Answer: Yes, this was a useful experience. It was interesting to read and analyze how my classmates completed this task. What approach did they take?

Alina P.

Attachment 3. Examples of classmates' essay evaluations upon completion of the chapter's materials.

Мargarita Малышева 10 дек 2024 в 20:32

Богдана, Bogdana's essay is as well executed as the last essay, which I also evaluated. The essay is organized logically: different aspects of the interview are highlighted, which makes the text consistent. Bogdana also uses specific examples (for example, preparing questions for Pavel Durov or mentioning John Sawatsky), which adds depth to her essay and demonstrates the real application of the theory. The language of the text is professional and written competently, it uses fairly accurate formulations. The text shows that Bogdana not only read the chapter, but also comprehended it, applying it to her experience and plans. In general, I don't see any serious mistakes in the essay, I like its structure and the rest that I mentioned above.

Ответить

♡ 1

Надежда Кин 10 дек 2024 в 20:54

Полина, I really enjoyed Polina's essay. At the beginning, she introduces the reader to the topic, giving a general idea of the essence of the interview, and shares her personal opinion about the preference for written works over interviews, which creates a contrast.

Polina also highlights the key aspects of the interview: visual dialogue, freedom of form and audience involvement. She convincingly explains why this is attractive to journalists and the audience, which emphasizes her analytical skills. In addition, Polina focuses on the development of the interview in the context of visual media, which indicates her awareness of modern trends in journalism.

The essay demonstrates a good understanding of the interview genre and its role in the modern information space. At the same time, I want to wish Polina not to be afraid of such types of work, because in any work everything can get out of control. I think that Polina, if she wants, will be able to become a good interviewer.

Ответить

♡ 1

Арина Баранова 10 дек 2024 в 21:29

Мargarita, Margarita described the chapter briefly and clearly in her essay, which can easily be used even to repeat the material, if necessary. I think this is a plus of her work, as you can see that she really delved into the material and tried to remember as much of it as possible.

But I didn't have enough of Margarita herself in the essay. The description is really a good moment of work, but still I wanted to know her impressions of the chapter. For example, what became the most interesting thing for her there. This disadvantage does not spoil the essay itself, it makes it more about facts and material, which cannot be called a bad job.

Ответить

♡ 1

FEATURES OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS:

In terms of the application of the selected educational material, it is important to emphasize the reliance on the principles of **interactivity and student involvement** in the process, which contributes to a deeper acquisition of professional vocabulary and the development of communication skills, not just critical thinking, but its application in the future professional sphere. It is important to build a transparent format of group work and a positive attitude to learning, when all participants in the process understand the goals and objectives, are motivated to achieve the result, for which it is worth giving students more autonomy and rights in solving educational issues.

To achieve these goals, the following steps should be used in the process of work:

- Together, in the format of an equal dialogue with students, determine priorities and goals, discuss the content of the course, and if the teacher independently selects educational materials, it is worth giving students the opportunity to take responsibility for their learning, involving them in decision-making. A sense of control gives not only an awareness of responsibility but also increases students' interest in achieving the desired and expected result.

In the described experience, together with the students, we identified the chapters that aroused the greatest professional interest and even the order of studying them (since it seemed impossible to complete the entire book in only 48 hours of classroom work).

- The use of modern technologies and interactive teaching methods (work in pairs and mini-groups, projects and case studies, online resources, etc.) allows to increase the level of activity and

involvement of students, which contributes to a deeper understanding and assimilation of the material; stimulates interest in the studied subject, increases motivation, and promotes the formation of independence and a creative approach to learning; in the process of group discussions and projects, students develop communication, cooperation, and critical thinking skills, which are important for their future professional activities.

The practical application of these principles has shown not only that such results are achievable, but also that students learn to recognize their role in the learning process, analyze their actions and results. Immersion in problem-solving situations that are related closely to future professional activities makes learning more meaningful and practice-oriented. Interactive methods allowed each student to actively participate in the learning process, which is especially important for weaker students, who also received additional support from their classmates.

- The ability of students to self-assess and evaluate the progress of their classmates is an essential component of autonomy. It is worthwhile to expand opportunities for the exchange of experiences, knowledge and opinions between students, as this always evokes a deep emotional response and increases involvement in the learning process.

In the learning process in this example, these principles of work were applied both in the form of reviews of the work of classmates in the study group in VK and in the form of discussions of joint and individual projects in the classroom. The following results were noted: the formation of the ability to give constructive feedback and the development of analytical abilities, the development of intra-group communication and the creation of a supportive learning environment, increased awareness of mistakes and self-correction.

However, on this path to achieving positive results, it is worth avoiding the following pitfalls: students may overestimate their peers' grades due to friendly relations or unwillingness to criticize, so it is worth initially proposing or developing through joint discussion the evaluation criteria, it is necessary to prepare students and clearly explain the need for this step and the benefits received from it. The process of peer evaluation requires additional time and effort, which implies a clear definition of adequate deadlines for completing these tasks.

- It is necessary to introduce into the learning process all possible tools to increase students' independence. You can create a list of additional resources that students can access in the process of comprehending the material or use them for specific tasks. It is important to emphasize that access to authentic materials helps to understand the context more deeply and develops cultural competence.

Due to the fact that in the described experiment professional English for journalists was studied, we actively used digital versions of the most famous periodicals in the USA to search and analyze samples of the best professional works in journalism, for example, leads - a rating of the best leads in stories awarded the Pulitzer Prize. The students independently searched for materials on the Internet for various tasks, for example, the best and worst interviews, in their opinion.

- It is necessary to create a positive, trusting, and supportive learning environment in which students will feel confident, without experiencing a paralyzing fear of making mistakes, and will be ready to show creativity, which, subsequently, will allow them to apply the knowledge they have acquired in practice.

The application of all acquired knowledge and practical skills is embodied in the FINAL TASK. This final project was announced before the start of the semester itself, so that students could determine the scope of their professional interests and vision of what they want to present as a final project. Possible options corresponding to the specifics of the journalistic profile were agreed upon in advance: interview, (news) report, review (of a film, book, music album, etc.), etc. At the beginning of the semester, we discussed the topics of the final project and their compliance with the material being studied, personal and professional interests of students, the format of the final task. We also determined the stages of work on the projects and approximate dates for passing checkpoints, created groups in which students completed a task similar in format (for example, an interview).

At the beginning of the semester, the following steps corresponding to the 4 academic months from September to December were agreed upon during a group discussion: 1. Create rubrics/grading

scale. 2. Create a rough draft/script, discuss in groups, make changes based on the advice of classmates. 3. Preview projects and open discussion in groups. 4. Present the final project and evaluate it.

I consider the stage of creating rubrics/grading scales to be one of the most important. The students were given pre-selected examples of grading rubrics in English according to the project format (interview, report, review). Through discussions in specialized groups and consultations with teachers leading the relevant disciplines, the students developed professionally oriented grading scales for the final project in Russian and translated it into English. This became the first step in the students' understanding not just of what they wanted to present as the final assignment, but also of what they wanted their ideal result to be—they set the bar high for themselves. This psychological move, when a high result is not imposed from the outside but formulated by the participants in the process themselves, involves them in the activity more consciously, does not allow them to relax, and motivates them to achieve the best result.

It is important to emphasize the role of the teacher as a guide and coach in the process of preparing and implementing final projects. Although most of the work on preparation and discussion took place in specialized groups, control over the implementation of tasks and compliance with deadlines still remains the teacher's responsibility. Moreover, as practice has shown, teachers can give advice, even without being specialists in journalism, simply relying on their life experience and the general impression of the students' projects.

At the stage of discussing the draft version of the projects, as practice has shown, there were no critical comments or problems. Moreover, in the specialized subgroups, issues with professional technical equipment and special programs necessary for the implementation of the projects were fixed. The students were able to cope with the English version even independently, without the help of the teacher. But at the stage of the preliminary demonstration, all the rough spots and problems emerged, which were resolved during the discussion in the specialized groups and with the teacher.

From student reviews:

Are you satisfied with your final project? Highlight its strengths and weaknesses? I am satisfied with my project. Thanks to the group discussion, we shared our opinions on the shortcomings and strengths of each submitted project before the final assessment, so it seems to me that there are no problems with it. In my project, I like the editing, splicing, the music selected for each section, and the sound quality.

Margarita M.

The final project was the culmination of the semester. The presentations of the final versions of the final project took place in the last two classes of the semester. The excitement of the students was noticeable as they presented the results of their several months' worth of work to their classmates. The students preferred not to invite third-party experts for assessment; therefore, the scores on the developed scales were provided by classmates anonymously, in a personal message in VK, with requisite justification using the rubrics developed in advance, and from the teacher, calculated according to the arithmetic mean (the sum of all points divided by the number of survey participants). The grades obtained by calculating the arithmetic mean of all the grades that were given by classmates and me varied from 16 to 20 maximum points. All the works presented demonstrated the diligence of the students who had completed a professional project in English.

From student reviews:

Your impressions of completing the final project in the form of a professionally oriented assignment in English. Answer: This assignment brought me many pleasant impressions. It was interesting to look at the work of my classmates, to find out what they are interested in, who and what inspires them, and also to share my own information. It was interesting to search for information, to work with the English language, and, of course, to create the video product itself.

Elizaveta S.

My own CONCLUSIONS after the end of the semester: I had to act not only as an expert in English (since we often encountered specific terms that required my help in translation) but also to become one in journalism, since I studied along with my students. At the beginning of the semester, I formulated a message for the students: "You are the (future) specialists here; I can only help you with language issues," which, by the way, helped many to become more confident and state their opinions on the topics discussed in the semester; however, due to the specifics of practical assignments in the journalism profile, the students and I managed to discuss a fairly wide range of topics: from education and culture to current military conflicts and other hard news. The most important thing was that everybody tried to actively participate in discussions and other assignments, trying to express their opinions and develop a practical professional set of skills.

Many varieties of formative assessment (essay-reflection at the end of chapters, assessment of classmates' work, etc.) were new to students, and I had to devote a lot of attention to explaining in class how to correctly complete these tasks, to talk through their structure. Also, after the first experience of completing these tasks, we discussed with the students all the challenges they had faced. By the end of the semester, all participants did not experience any difficulties.

At the end of the semester, a survey (which was presented as a suggestion, not a requirement) was completed in a group of 18 people, in which 15 people took part. Analysis of the students' questionnaires based on the results of the semester showed that most of them rated the process of completing the final assignment as quite difficult: the average difficulty rating by students was 6 out of 10 (range from 1 to 9).

The greatest difficulties were caused by technical aspects (editing, sound, equipment)—mentioned by 70% of students; the language barrier (pronunciation, professional vocabulary)—40%; and coordinating schedules and assessment criteria—25%. It is worth noting that students who chose familiar formats (for example, film reviews) perceived the tasks as easy (grades 1–3).

In assessing the effectiveness of support during project implementation, the rating of assistance methods (by frequency of mentions as "the most useful") showed that 60% of students put individual consultations with the teacher in 1st or 2nd place, which clearly demonstrates the importance of the teacher's role in students' independent project work - an important psychological moment for those colleagues who are afraid to hand everything over to the students. Students also noted step-by-step planning and setting clear deadlines as important factors in organizing work on the final assignment; therefore, I will again emphasize the importance of dialogue (it is necessary to discuss with students in advance the checkpoints that are comfortable for them in terms of deadlines) and the role of the teacher as the curator of the process of completing everything on time. It is interesting to note the ambiguous assessment of work in specialized groups: for some students, this became a motivating factor, for others - a source of stress. Most participants rated the discussion of projects before the presentation as useful, but it was noted that the process itself requires a clearer structure.

The following aspects of the final project were critically assessed: 5 questionnaires noted a lack of clear evaluation criteria, which for me showed the importance of additional analysis of the rubrics before launching them into work. Also, 30% of respondents felt uncomfortable with the anonymity of the assessment of classmates' work. A request was formulated for an alternative, for example, open discussions with feedback. Although this issue should be openly discussed at the beginning of the semester and take into account the opinion of the majority of students, in this parameter I reserve the right for the majority to indicate the preference of this assessment format: in the anonymous for classmates option, students can more objectively, critically evaluate each other's work.

80% of students were satisfied with the final project, especially those who worked with topics of their personal interests (interviews, reviews). All students highlighted the following as strengths in completing the final project: creativity, practical experience, and improvement of language skills. As weaknesses in each other's work, students pointed out technical errors (sound, editing), and lack of depth of analysis.

In the part of the questionnaire where the survey was conducted regarding the educational materials of the specialized semester, the following positive aspects were named: expansion of

professional vocabulary (90% of responses), practical focus (filming, media analysis), usefulness of essays on the results of completed chapters for self-reflection (but 20% of students considered them formal). Students saw problems in the overload of terms (especially those who initially had a lower level of language) and in the lack of time to discuss complex topics.

The analysis of these data showed the need to modify some aspects of the work in the specialized semester, for example, to provide clearer criteria and examples of successful works in order to avoid the feeling of formality in the case of reflective essays and to offer alternative formats of reflection (audio/video diaries). The overload of terms (especially for students with a low level of language) can be solved by adding visualization of terms (infographics, diagrams, memes), conducting periodic repetitions in a game form (quizzes). In the case of a study group with mixed contrasting levels of language proficiency, it is possible to introduce a gradation of difficulty (for example, dividing materials into "basic" and "advanced"). It seems advisable to introduce peer-to-peer mentoring support for students with a low level of language provided by those with a higher linguistic level. Gamification can also be used (points, badges for activity) to increase motivation. Regarding the lack of time to discuss complex topics, some of the discussions can be moved to an asynchronous format (forums, chats, voice messages in VK and/or Telegram).

In the end-of-semester questionnaire, I also asked students to formulate their suggestions for improving the format of working with the material. The students' request indicated the need for clarification and introduction of clear criteria and transparency of assessment for activity during the lessons and a balance of theory and practice in classes - more interactive tasks (role-playing games, case analysis), less "routine" discussions of texts.

An analysis of the students' questionnaires showed that the general impression of the professional English language studies was positive for the majority: the connection of the studied materials with the future profession, the creative approach, and the growth of motivation (especially among interested students) were noted. The negative aspects included an overload of materials (the results of other questionnaires show that, in general, students fail to cope with current assignments mostly due to an overload of studies) and unclear requirements.

From student reviews:

Please share your overall impression.

I am sincerely grateful for such an interesting approach to studying not just English language material but professionally oriented material. All the information was absolutely useful, I learned a lot of things that I could not even guess about. I noticed that I worked more actively this time. I think that this is all thanks to the information that was interesting to me. The tasks were always quite unusual, even requiring creativity, which I really liked. Of course, it was sometimes difficult, but the difficulties were easy to cope with. In general, it was very interesting and informative, and most importantly, useful for my future work as a journalist.

Elizaveta S.

I learned a lot of new things about my profession that we were not taught in specialized subjects. There was also a lot of useful practice and interactive tasks that helped develop soft skills) I think that in my further study of English, I will use our textbook; there are many interesting chapters left in it that will help me study my profession even more deeply.

Diana Z.

I am grateful to the 3rd semester and the English course in general; it allowed me to advance in the language, delve deeper into certain points, and develop skills not only in foreign language but also in journalism.

Alina P.

The practical conclusion for me as a teacher was the success of this format of conducting classes in the specialized semester as a practical tool for learning the language. But it is also clear to me that the format requires improvement in several aspects, in particular in structuring (clear stages, criteria) and adaptation and flexibility (taking into account the different levels of preparation and workload of students). It is important to maintain a constant dialogue with students to assess the effectiveness of both the materials and the form of work with them, for example, to conduct regular micro-surveys, based on the results of which to make the necessary changes.

In addition to helping colleagues broaden their professional toolkit, I hope that the work experience and applied practices described will enhance the perspectives of those who encounter comparable tasks.